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Parental Involvement and Counselling Services as Predictors of Effective Career Decision Making among Secondary School Students in Ido Local Government, Oyo State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined parental involvement and counselling services as predictors of career decision making among secondary school students in Ido local government area of Oyo state, Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design was adopted. The sample consisted of 250 senior secondary schools' students selected through stratified random sampling technique from various schools in the area. A well-structured questionnaire was used as the primary instrument for data collection. The instrument trial tested and found to be valid and reliable with reliability coefficient of 0.74. They study sought to determine the composite and relative contribution of parental involvement and counselling services in career decision making among secondary school students. The data were analyzed using correlation and multiple regression analysis. The results indicated that both parental involvement and counselling services significantly correlated with career decision making. Also, parental involvement and counselling services significantly predicted career decision making among the students used for the study with counselling services showing a slightly stronger influence. The study concluded that students' career decision making can be substantially enhanced through improved parental engagement and well-coordinated school counselling programmes. It recommended that school administrations and policymakers should prioritize these two factors to foster career decision making among students.

Keywords: Parental involvement, Counselling services, Career decision making, Secondary school students

INTRODUCTION

Career decision making is a critical aspect of an individual's life, influencing their future direction and success for secondary school students, making informed and effective career decision is essential as it sets the foundation for their professional lives in Ido local government of Oyo State, Nigeria. The role of parental involvement and counselling services in shaping students career decisions cannot be overemphasised. These factors significantly impact students' awareness, understanding and choice regarding their future careers.

In Nigeria, the education system aims to prepare students for both higher education and the workforce.

However, many students face challenges in making well-informed career decision due to a lack of guidance, exposure and support. Parental involvement and school-based counselling services are two critical elements that can bridge this gap, providing students with the necessary information, encouragement and support to make sound career choices.

Career decision is the process of choosing a particular career path or job, often involving considerations such as personal interests, skills, values, opportunities for growth and financial benefits. Making a career decision typically involves evaluating different options, seeking advice and reflecting on one's long-term goals. Career decision making is the process of selecting a career path or making decisions about your professional life. It involves exploring your interest, values, skills and personality and find a career that aligns with who you are and what you want to achieve. Amundson (2006) career decision making is a dynamic and interactive process involving exploration, reflective and action. Ezeani (2016) career decision making involves using self-awareness exploration and planning to make informed career choices. Omoniyi (2016) career decision making is a process of integrating one's identity, values and context to make meaningful career choices.

Parental involvement refers to the active participation of parents in their children's education and career planning. This can include attending school meeting, providing guidance on career choices and being involved in school activities. Parental involvement is a multifaceted concept that plays a critical role in student's educational success. Scholars like Ajibola (2015), Ezeani (2016) and Ibrahim and Yusuf (2019) have contributed significantly to our understanding of how different forms of parental involvement impact children's academic and social development. Parental involvement in education encompasses various activities through which parents support their children's academic and career development. This involvement is crucial during the secondary school years when students begin to seriously consider their future career paths.

Educational Support, parents provide assistance with homework, monitor academic progress and attend parent teacher meetings. This support ensures that students are academically prepared for future career opportunities. Career Guidance: Parents discuss career options with their children, share information about different professions and help them explore their interest and strengths. Emotional and motivational support: Parents offer encouragement, boost their children's confidence and create a positive environment for learning.

Counseling Services in schools provide students with professional support to address educational, personal and career challenges. Effective counselling services may include: Career counseling: Counselors help students understand their interests and strengths, explore various career paths and plan their career paths (Adekeye, 2017). This support is critical for helping students make informed career decisions. Counsellors assist students with academic planning, addressing learning difficulties and setting academic goals. Academic counseling ensures that students are on track to achieve their educational objectives (FME, 2013). Counsellors provide student's well-being and academic performance by addressing these issues, counsellors help students to maintain a healthy balance between their personal lives and academic responsibilities.

Statement of the Problem

In Ido Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria, secondary school students are faced with significant challenges in making informed career decisions. This problem is compounded by the limited availability of career counselling services and varying levels of parental involvement in the educational and career process of these students. The absence of structured career guidance of inconsistent parental support often leaves student with inadequate information and guidance, with negativity. Failure to make adequate and effective career decision as at when due could mar the future of individual to extend that the individual could miss it for life time. In the light of this the researcher decided to find out the role played by these two variables – parental involvement and effective counselling services in enhancing effective career decision making among secondary school students in Ido Local Government area of Oyo State Ibadan, Nigeria. The issue of Career decision making had been researched on by many researchers some on psychological intervention, some on determinants factors while some used predictive factors approach to

find out factors militating against career decision making. This present study is based on parental involvement and effective counselling services which no researcher has never combined in seeking for effective career decision making.

Purpose of the Study

The primary objectives of this study are: to determine the relationship between the level of parental involvement and counselling services in the career decision making process of secondary school students in Ido Local Government. Also, to evaluate the composite and relative contribution of counselling services and parental involvement in career decision making among secondary school students.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between independent variables (parental involvement and counselling services) in career decision making among secondary school students in Ido local government, Oyo state?
2. What is the composite contribution of parental involvement and counselling services in the career decision making process of secondary school students?
3. What is the relative contribution of parental involvement and counselling services in the career decision making process of secondary school students?

METHODOLOGY

Design

The study adopted a descriptive research design of correlational type. This design is appropriate because it allows for the examination of the relationship between parental involvement, counselling services and students' career decision-making. The survey approach enables data collection from a large number of respondents to establish patterns and relationships

Population

The population of the study consisted of Senior Secondary School students (SS1 - SS3) in public and private schools in Ido Local Government area.

Sampling Techniques

A sample size of 300 respondents were randomly selected based on the Yamane formula for determining sample size from a large population. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to ensure a fair representation of population of interest. Stratified sampling was used to categorize schools into public and private schools. Random sampling technique was used to choose schools from each category. The students from selected school were selected simple random sampling. Six school were randomly chosen 2 privates and 4 public school and the respondents were chosen with ratio 1:2, that 100 from private and 200 from public secondary schools.

Instrument for Data Collection

A structured questionnaire was used as the primary instrument for data collection. The questionnaire consisted of four sections. The demographic section (age, gender, school type, education, level of parents, etc). Section B: Parental involvement scale (items measuring parental support, career discussions at home and level of engagement in education. Section C: Counseling services scale (availability, accessibility and perceived effectiveness of counseling services in schools. While Section D: Career Decision-making scale (students' self-efficacy, knowledge of career options and readiness for career choices). The Likert response format was used for the instrument ie. A 4-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree) was used to collect data from respondents. The questionnaire was validated by experts in tests and measurement by carried out pilot study using 30 respondents outside the study area. The internal consistency of the questionnaire was measured using Cronbach's Alpha with a reliability coefficient of 0.73.

Data Collection Procedure

Permission from school authorities and relevant education boards preceded the collection of the data and this was followed by distribution of the questionnaire to selected students. The respondents were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaires and the completed questionnaires were retrieved from the respondents for data analysis.

Data Analysis Method

The collected Data were analyzed using quantitative statistical methods of descriptive Statistics and Inferential statistics of Pearson product moment correlation analysis was used to examine the relationship between parental involvement, counseling services, and career decision-making. While a multiple regression analysis was adopted to determine the predictive power of parental involvement and counseling services on students' career decision-making.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What is the relationship between independent variables (parental involvement and counselling services) in career decision making among secondary school students in Ido local government, Oyo state?*

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics and Correlations Matrix among the variables

	1	2	3
Career Decision Making	1.000		
Parental Involvement	.586**	1.000	
Counselling Effectiveness	.483**	.575**	1.000
Mean	26.240	23.290	21.620
Std. Deviation	10.894	5.091	6.841

The results from Table1 showed that there is significant relationship between parental involvement and effectiveness of counselling services and career decision making among secondary school students in Ido Local Government Area Ibadan of Oyo state, Nigeria ($r = 0.586, p < 0.05$) and ($r = 0.483$ and $p < 0.05$) respectively. Since $p < 0.05$, it implies that there is significant relationship between parental involvement and career decision making among secondary school students in Ido Local Government Ibadan of Oyo state, Nigeria.

Research Question Two: *What is the combine influence of independent variables (parental involvement and effectiveness of counselling services) on career decision making among secondary school students in Ido Local Government Ibadan of Oyo state, Nigeria?*

Table 2: Joint contribution of the independent variables

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.984 ^a	.968	.967	1.49697

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	6521.462	2	3260.731	3743.661	.000 ^b
Residual	215.128	247	0.871		
Total	6736.590	249			

Table 2 shows that there was the joint contribution of the independent variables (parental involvement and effectiveness of counselling services) on career decision making among secondary school students in Ido Local Government Ibadan of Oyo state; $R = 0.984$, $p < .05$. The table further reveals 96.7% (Adj. $R^2 = 0.967$) of the variance in the career decision making among secondary school students in Ido Local Government Area of Ibadan, Oyo state were accountable for by the linear combination of the independent variables. The ANOVA results from the regression analysis show a significant contribution of the independent variables on the dependent variables; $F(2, 247) = 3743.661$, $p < 0.05$. It implies a significant joint contribution of the independent variables on career decision making among secondary school students in Ido Local Government Area, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Research Question Three. *What is the relative influence of independent variables (parental involvement and effectiveness of counselling services) on career decision making among secondary school students in Ido Local Government Ibadan of Oyo state, Nigeria?*

Table 3: Relative Contribution of the Independent Variables on the Dependent Variable

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.329	1.248		1.866	.065
	Parental Involvement	.550	.036	.444	5.673	.000
	Counselling Service	.267	.027	.169	2.066	.000

Table 3 above shows that all two independent variables significantly contribute to career decision making among students in Ido LG Ibadan. The variables include the following: parental involvement ($\beta = 0.444$, $t = 5.673$, $p < 0.05$) and counselling services ($\beta = 0.169$, $t = 2.066$, $p < 0.05$). It was observed that parental involvement was more potent contributor to career decision making among secondary school students in Ibadan and counselling services was the least.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Based on the data gathered from the administered questionnaire, the study explored the relationship and predictive power of parental involvement and counseling services on students' ability to make effective career decisions. The findings are discussed below:

Influence of Parental Involvement on Career Decision-Making

The study revealed that parental involvement significantly influences students' career decision-making. Most students reported that their parents often engage in conversations about their future careers, monitor their academic progress, and provide guidance on career-related matters (Ibrahim and Yusuf, 2019). This supports prior research that suggests students with involved parents are more confident, better informed, and more likely to set realistic career goals. It also indicates that when parents are supportive and open to their children's interests, students are more likely to pursue careers aligned with their strengths and passions. From aforementioned the schools should organize regular parent-student forums and career talks to strengthen parental involvement and parents need to be educated about the importance of career counseling and their role in guiding their children constructively (Agba and Oboegbulem, 2015).

The study revealed that students whose parents are actively involved in their education and career planning tend to show greater confidence and clarity in their career goals. Similarly, students who have access to effective and supportive counseling services are better informed and more prepared to make meaningful career choices. Furthermore, the combined effect of parental support and school counseling

significantly increases students' ability to explore options, align their interests with potential careers, and plan for their future. However, challenges such as limited access to trained counselors, lack of structured career programs in some schools, and inadequate parental knowledge about modern career paths still persist (Atanda and Jaiyeoba, 2011; Esene, 2017 and Isiaka and Aremu, 2020).

In conclusion, for students in Ido Local Government—and by extension, other similar regions in Nigeria—to make effective career decisions, there must be intentional collaboration between parents, schools, and the wider community. Strengthening both parental involvement and counseling programs is essential to building a generation of students who are confident, informed, and ready to pursue fulfilling careers.

The study examined how parental involvement and school counseling services predict effective career decision-making among secondary school students in Ido Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria. The findings clearly underscore the significant and positive influence of these two factors on students' ability to make informed, confident, and realistic career choices.

Students whose parents were engaged in their academic and personal development exhibited stronger decision-making abilities. This involvement ranged from discussing career options, monitoring school performance, to supporting students' aspirations (Nduka, 2016). These results affirm that parents serve as a primary influence in the early stages of career development, and their encouragement enhances students' self-belief and future planning.

Impact of Counseling Services on Career Decision-Making

Responses from the students showed that access to counselling services positively impacts students' awareness and preparedness for career decision-making (Ajibola, 2015). Those who participated in counseling sessions reported having a clearer understanding of their strengths, available career paths, and educational requirements for different careers. The government and school administrators should ensure the availability of trained guidance counsellors in all secondary schools. Also, counseling services should be made more practical, student-focused, and tailored to the evolving job market (Adegbite, 2017).

On the other hand, the availability and quality of counseling services in schools were also identified as vital to effective career decision-making. Students who regularly accessed career counseling demonstrated a clearer understanding of their interests, skills, and potential career paths. However, the study also exposed gaps in the implementation of counseling services in many schools—mainly due to a shortage of professional counselors and lack of structured programs (Gbore, 2014).

Importantly, the joint influence of parental involvement and counseling services was found to be even more powerful. When both support systems work together, students receive balanced guidance that is both emotionally supportive and professionally informed. This dual influence ensures that students are not only inspired but also equipped with accurate information and skills for career planning (Chinyere, 2014).

Despite the positive findings, the study also acknowledged challenges such as cultural expectations, parental bias towards traditional careers, and limited awareness about emerging job markets. These issues, if unaddressed, can hinder students from exploring diverse career options or making independent choices (Omoniyi, 2016).

Joint Influence of Parental Involvement and Counseling Services

Regression analysis indicated that both parental involvement and counseling services are joint predictors of effective career decision-making. Their interaction provides a supportive environment for students, fostering both personal confidence and realistic goal setting. Students who received input from both parents and counselors were more decisive, better informed, and more committed to their career choices (Fayomi and Oyelade, 2020). The implication for this is that collaboration between parents and school counselors should be encouraged. And structured programs that integrate parental input into school-based career planning can enhance outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Parental involvement and counselling services are predictors of effective career decision-making among secondary school students in Ido Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria. Based on the findings, it can be concluded that both parental involvement and counselling services play a crucial and complementary role in shaping students' career decisions.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Educational workshops should be organized for parents by schools and local education authorities to enlighten them on their critical role in guiding their children's career paths.

Parents should be encouraged to engage regularly in school activities such as career days, PTA meetings, and open days to stay informed and involved in their children's academic and career development.

Home-based support (discussions, encouragement, and monitoring) should be emphasized as a strong foundation for career awareness.

Government and school authorities should employ more trained guidance and counseling professionals in all secondary schools within the LGA.

Regular career guidance programs, seminars, and mentorship sessions should be implemented to expose students to a wide range of career possibilities.

Counseling services should be student-centered, accessible, and tailored to individual needs, with periodic assessments to track student progress.

Schools should create a structured platform for collaboration between parents and counselors (e.g., joint career planning sessions, family counseling workshops).

Counselors should provide feedback to parents on students' career interests, strengths, and challenges, fostering shared responsibility in guiding students.

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